

PRESS RELEASE

Prepare young voters for the EP 2024 elections with EDUbox!

As the June 2024 European elections approach, educators are looking for effective ways to educate and empower young voters. There's a pressing need for accessible, ready-to-use learning material, and the new EDUbox on Politics is one of the resources addressing this demand.

EDUbox Politics aims to equip young voters with a deeper understanding of politics, crucial for their participation in the upcoming European Parliament (EP) 2024 elections. Divided into four engaging sections, it introduces politics through relatable scenarios, guides students through the journey of their vote, and encourages active participation and reflection.

Key Highlights:

- ✓ **Accessible Learning:** EDUbox Politics offers ready-to-use material adaptable to formal and non-formal educational settings, ideal for teaching about the EP 2024 elections.
- ✓ **Engaging Content:** Designed for student engagement, EDUbox incorporates various interactive elements, discussion prompts, and activities, fostering understanding and encouraging active participation in critical political discussions.
- ✓ **Proven Effectiveness:** The EDUmake project consortium partners tested this resource, receiving positive feedback from educators who appreciated its user-friendly interface, high-quality content, and effectiveness.

As the road to the 2024 European elections unfolds, educators are invited to use EDUbox Politics, empowering young voters with vital knowledge for active participation in shaping their future.

EDUbox Politics is currently available in English and Dutch (adapted for the Belgian context). At the beginning of 2024 it will also be available in Dutch (for the audience in the Netherlands) and Croatian.

For more information about this EDUbox and to access it, please visit media-and-learning.eu/project/edumake/. If you're interested in customising EDUbox Politics for your country, you can [complete the form](#) on the webpage or reach out to Tim van Lier (Tim.VANLIER@VRT.BE) for further details.

EDUmake consortium: VRT (national public-service broadcaster for the Flemish Community of Belgium), NTR (Dutch public broadcaster), imec (R&D and innovation hub in Belgium), **University of Zagreb** (Croatia) and **Media & Learning Association**.

